

Appendix B

Example of a learning unit integrating exemplars, shared criteria, peer assessment, and self-assessment

Educational context

The learning unit was designed for a fifth-grade primary school class (24 students) located in Northern Italy. The class was characterized by a positive and collaborative climate, fostered through active and laboratory-based approaches experienced in previous years. Students were accustomed to working in groups and generally demonstrated autonomy, curiosity, and motivation.

The school environment included digital devices (tablets and interactive whiteboards) and a computer laboratory. Classroom furniture was arranged in clusters to support communication, collaboration, and active participation.

The unit focused on Geography and addressed six Northern Italian regions through collaborative inquiry and digital presentations.

Learning objectives

The unit aimed to enable students to:

- identify the main physical, social, and economic characteristics of a Northern Italian region;
- analyse information from different sources;
- collaboratively produce a digital presentation;
- develop evaluative judgement through peer assessment and self-assessment practices.

Learning sequence

Phase 1. Co-construction of quality criteria through exemplars

Students, organised into six groups, analysed two presentations of different quality (one complete and one incomplete) displayed on the interactive whiteboard. Through guided questions (“What makes a presentation clear and complete?” and “Which information should be included?”), students discussed similarities and differences between the two examples.

Using the digital platform Wooclap, students shared their ideas and, with teacher facilitation, collaboratively developed criteria describing the characteristics of a high-quality presentation.

Phase 2. Collaborative research and production

Each group was assigned one Northern Italian region and received the shared criteria together with a checklist designed to support self-monitoring.

Using textbooks, maps and digital resources, students collected information and collaboratively created a digital presentation. During the process, the teacher conducted systematic observations and provided formative feedback.

Phase 3. Peer assessment and revision

After completing their presentations, groups exchanged their work anonymously.

Using a peer-assessment rubric based on previously shared criteria, students evaluated another group’s presentation and provided written and oral feedback. Afterwards, groups received the feedback on their own work and revised their presentations accordingly.

This phase aimed to promote evaluative judgement, reflection, and students’ active engagement in assessment processes.

Phase 4. Oral presentation and self-assessment

Groups presented their work to the whole class. At the end of the activity, students completed an individual self-assessment form to reflect on:

- what they had learned;
- what they found difficult;
- how they collaborated within the group;
- aspects they still needed to improve.

Assessment practices embedded in the learning unit:

Phase	Assessment purpose	Assessment tools
Construction of criteria	Assessment for learning	Exemplars, classroom discussion
Collaborative production	Formative assessment	Teacher observations, checklist
Peer review	Assessment for learning	Peer-assessment rubric and feedback
Oral presentation	Formative and summative assessment	Teacher rubric
Reflection	Sustainable assessment	Self-assessment form

Students collaboratively identified the following criteria for a high-quality presentation:

- ❖ Content
 - physical characteristics of the region;
 - major cities and population;
 - cultural aspects and traditions;
 - economic activities.
- ❖ Language
 - clarity of explanations;
 - appropriate use of geographical terminology.
- ❖ Visual design
 - orderly slides;
 - inclusion of maps, images, and graphs.
- ❖ Collaboration
 - active participation of all group members.

Peer-assessment prompts

Students were asked to answer the following questions:

1. What did you appreciate most about this presentation?
2. Was the presentation clear and understandable?
3. What could be improved?
4. What suggestions would you give to your peers?

Self-assessment prompts

At the end of the unit, students reflected on the following questions:

- What did you enjoy most?
- What did you learn?
- What did you find difficult?
- How did you work with your group?
- What should you improve?